

PROBIOTIC GRANULE DEVELOPMENT FOR POTENTIAL PHYCOCYANIN AND *LACTOBACILLUS ACIDOPHILUS* ATCC 4356

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, probiotics are popular because they are good for health. They are often used in food and medicine products. Many granules contain *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, but potential phycocyanin used with *Lactobacillus acidophilus* are not studied. In this study, the effects of phycocyanin and maltodextrin on *Lactobacillus acidophilus* ATCC 4356 were tested to develop probiotic granules. The granules were prepared by a wet granulation method using phycocyanin, maltodextrin and skim milk. The results showed that the bacterium could survive well in 5% maltodextrin and 3% phycocyanin. The survival rate in the granules was about 90 ± 4.7 to $95 \pm 2\%$ although they were stored at on month. The study pointed out phycocyanin can be used to formulate with *Lactobacillus acidophilus* ATCC 4356 in granule products.

KEYWORDS: granules, *Lactobacillus acidophilus* ATCC 4356, phycocyanin, viability.

INTRODUCTION

Probiotics are live microorganisms that are good for health. When people take enough probiotics, they can help improve the digestive system. It is difficult to say the exact dose for probiotics. Some products work well at a low dose (about 1-10 billion CFU per dose), while

others need a higher dose to be effective. Therefore, the correct dosage should be carefully studied, and people should ask a doctor or expert to get the best health benefits. Probiotics are found a lot in foods like yoghurt and cheese. They can live in the intestines and help keep the gut clean and balanced. They are good for the digestive system and can help reduce some stomach problems like ulcers, bloating, food poisoning, diarrhea, constipation, and irritable bowel syndrome. Probiotics can also compete with harmful bacteria in the body. They help improve the immune system and make the body stronger. In addition, they help people digest lactose better, so children may have less bloating or stomach discomfort when eating dairy foods. Besides that, probiotics can provide some important nutrients for the body, such as folic acid, niacin, riboflavin, and vitamins B6 and B12 (Fuller, 1991).

Lactobacillus acidophilus (*L. acidophilus*) is the most widely examined probiotic strains in the genus *Lactobacillus* that can produce lactic acid and mainly found in human intestines. *L. acidophilus* is Gram-positive bacteria, rod-shaped, non-spore forming, capable of aerobic and anaerobic fermentation, often present in the small intestine and help to balance the intestinal microflora, is considered a natural antibiotic against harmful microorganisms. *L. acidophilus* has main effects such as generate several strong antibiotics in the gut to help prevent the growth of some pathogenic microorganisms. Also, its enzyme lactase production helps to break down carbohydrates reducing the growth of tumours, able to effectively neutralize as well as prevent carcinogens and lowers cholesterol in the blood (Di Cerbo *et al.*, 2016). *L. acidophilus* can grow at temperatures from 37 to 42 °C (Altermann *et al.*, 2005), pH 5.5 – 6.0 (Shah, 2007) and requires complex nutritions for cultivation (Gomes and Malcata, 1999). The nutrient-rich De Man, Rogosa and Sharpe (MRS) medium (De Man *et al.*, 1960) is a selective culture medium designed to favour the growth of *Lactobacilli*.

Phycocyanin is a natural blue substance from *Spirulina platensis*. It is good for health and is used in food and medicine. Phycocyanin is a strong antioxidant. It helps protect the body from harmful substances. It can also help protect good bacteria like *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356 during drying and storage. Phycocyanin can reduce inflammation. This is good for the stomach and gut. It may help people feel better if they have digestive problems.

Phycocyanin is safe and easy to use. It dissolves in water, so it can be added to many products like drinks or granules. It also gives a natural blue color, so we do not need artificial color. Therefore, phycocyanin is important because it is healthy, safe, and useful in probiotic products (Pez Jaeschke *et al.*, 2021; Soliman *et al.*, 2025).

Granulation is a common method in making medicines. It is simple and does not need high technology. In this process, small powder particles are mixed and added with liquid to make a wet mass. Then, this mass is passed through a sieve and dried to form granules. Granules are stronger and more stable than powder. They help improve the uniformity of the mixture and make it easier to compress and flow when taken by mouth. The size of granules is usually from 0.2 mm to 4.0 mm (Shanmugam, 2015). Sometimes, granules are put into capsules. This form is easier to control and flows better than very fine powder.

A study showed that capsules made from enteric-coated granules of *L. acidophilus* can protect the bacteria well from artificial gastric juice. The capsule form is also used in the drying process and can be easily prepared. The enteric coating is important because it protects probiotics from the strong acid in the stomach. It also helps control the release of *L. acidophilus* in the intestine. This can improve the activity of probiotics, help replace harmful bacteria, and increase the survival rate in the human gut. However, when *L. acidophilus* is made into granules by the wet granulation method, it is difficult to keep the bacteria alive. Some studies showed that the survival rate of the bacteria after granulation is quite low (Sahni *et al.*, 2014).

The aim of this study is to make granules with *L. acidophilus* in phycocyanin that could maintain the bacteria survival.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bacterial strain

L. acidophilus ATCC 4356 was used in the study.

Ingredients

Maltodextrin was supported by Biopharco company (Vietnam).

Phycocyanin was obtained from Sigma (USA).

METHODS

Preparation of cell suspensions

The MRS medium was used to grow and keep the bacterium alive in this study. *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356 was grown in sterile MRS broth (pH 7.0) at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 48 hours. The culture was checked for purity and then spread on MRS agar. The plates were cultured at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 24–48 hours. The number of bacteria was counted by serial

dilution and spread plate method on MRS agar. The broth tubes which were checked for the CFU were stored at -80°C before the granulation process (Woraharn *et al.*, 2010).

Determination of the influence of maltodextrin on the growth of *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356

Maltodextrin is a food ingredient made from starch such as maize, wheat, and potato (Mollan and çLelik, 1996). It is a white powder with neutral taste (BeMiller and Whistler, 2009). It is often used to improve texture and as a filler. In this study, maltodextrin was used as an excipient, a viscosity agent, and a filler in granules. Different concentrations of maltodextrin (1%, 2%, 3%, 4%, and 5% w/v) were added into MRS medium. The media were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 90 minutes. Then, *Lactobacillus acidophilus* was cultured in these media and incubated at 37°C with 5% CO_2 for 48 hours. After that, the cultures were diluted and spread on MRS agar plates. The plates were incubated, and the number of colonies was counted to check how maltodextrin affected the survival of the bacteria.

Determination of the influence of phycocyanin on the growth of *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356

In this study, different concentrations of phycocyanin were added into MRS medium to get the final concentrations (1%, 2%, 3%). The bacterium from the stocks was cultured in the phycocyanin having media. All the mixturte were incubated at 37°C with 5% CO_2 for 48 hours. After that, the cultures were diluted and spread on MRS agar plates. The plates were incubated, and the number of colonies was counted to check how phycocyanin affected the survival of the bacterium.

Preparation of granules containing *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356

Granules of *L. acidophilus* were made by a wet granulation method. A suitable amount of maltodextrin, phycocyanin were mixed in distilled water that was sterilized at 121°C . Excipients such as Avicel 101 and skim milk powder were weighed and mixed with suspension containing maltodextrin and phycocyanin to form a wet paste. The paste was passed through a sieve (1.4 mm) and then dried at room temperature (about 25°C).

Viable count assay of *L. acidophilus* in granules

1.0 g of granules was dissolved in 10 mL of MRS medium (pH 7.0). The sample was diluted step by step (tenfold dilution) to get suitable concentration for counting. The number of *L. acidophilus* cells was counted by plate count method on MRS agar. The plates were

incubated at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 72 hours (Champagne *et al.*, 2011). The results were shown as log CFU/mL or CFU/g. The granules were checked at different times (3, 6, and 9 days) at room temperature to see the survival of the bacteria. The number of bacteria (CFU) was calculated by using a formula.

$$\text{Number of bacteria (CFU/mL or CFU/g)} = \frac{\text{Average colony count}}{(\text{Dilution plated}) \times (\text{amount plated})}$$

Statistical analysis

In this study, all experiments were done three times. The results were shown as mean ± standard deviation. Statistical tests like Student's t-test and one-way ANOVA were used to compare the results. These tests help to see if there are differences between the groups.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determination of the influence of maltodextrin on the growth of *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356

Lactobacillus acidophilus ATCC 4356 was grown in MRS medium with different levels of maltodextrin (1%, 2%, 3%, 4%, 5%) for 48 hours at 37°C with 5% CO₂. The number of live bacteria is shown in Table 1. The results show that changing maltodextrin from 1% to 5% did not change the survival of the bacteria much. Also, higher maltodextrin made better granule texture and higher viscosity. So, 5% maltodextrin was chosen for making granules.

Table 1: CFU count of *L. acidophilus* in different concentrations of maltodextrin.

Concentration of Maltodextrin	Standard plate count (CFU/mL)
1%	$2.20 \times 10^9 \pm 4.00 \times 10^8$
2%	$2.60 \times 10^9 \pm 6.24 \times 10^8$
3%	$2.37 \times 10^9 \pm 3.79 \times 10^8$
4%	$2.03 \times 10^9 \pm 3.21 \times 10^8$
5%	$2.80 \times 10^9 \pm 3.61 \times 10^8$

In phycocyanin condition, phycocyanin (3%) did not show the survival effects on the bacterial growth (Table 2). Phycocyanin can be used as colorant and biological compound, therefore, phycocyanin (3%) was preferred to formulate with the bacterium to make probiotic.

Table 2: CFU count of *L. acidophilus* in different concentrations of phycocyanin.

Concentration of Phycocyanin	Standard plate count (CFU/mL)
1%	$1.24 \times 10^9 \pm 2.02 \times 10^8$
2%	$1.26 \times 10^9 \pm 1.81 \times 10^8$
3%	$1.18 \times 10^9 \pm 2.53 \times 10^8$

Granule preparation containing *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356

The optimized formulation of probiotic granules containing *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356 was presented in Table 3. The formulation consisted of 3% phycocyanin, 1% Avicel 101, 5% maltodextrin, and 2–3% skim milk powder as excipients.

Table 3: The formulations of granules containing *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356.

Components	Concentrations
Avicel 101	1%
Maltodextrin	5%
Phycocyanin	3%
Skim milk powder	2-3%

The formulated granules were showed in figure 1. The granules had blue color. The colour was stable. Despite achieving a stable formulation, the resulting granules exhibited particle sizes that did not comply with the standard sieve range (0.2–1.4 mm). Specifically, a significant fraction of granules remained oversized and failed to pass through the sieve system. Morphologically, the granules were observed to possess a dense and compact structure, with high mechanical strength and resistance to fragmentation.

Figure 1: Granules containing phycocyanin and *L. acidophilus*.

This phenomenon can be attributed to several formulation-related factors. First, Avicel 101, a widely used binder and filler, contributes significantly to inter-particle cohesion through hydrogen bonding and plastic deformation during granulation. At the selected concentration (1%), it likely enhanced the structural integrity of the granules, resulting in increased

hardness. Second, maltodextrin at 5% acts as both a binder and a film-forming agent, further reinforcing the internal matrix of the granules. The combination of these two excipients may have led to excessive binding forces, producing granules with low friability.

Additionally, skim milk powder, commonly used as a protective agent for probiotics, contains proteins (casein, whey proteins) and lactose, which can contribute to matrix densification during drying. Protein aggregation and sugar crystallization may have further reduced porosity, limiting the ability of the granules to break apart under mechanical stress. This dense microstructure is unfavorable for achieving uniform particle size distribution and may negatively impact downstream processing, such as encapsulation or sachet filling.

From a functional perspective, overly hard granules may also influence the release behavior of probiotic cells. A compact matrix can delay water penetration and reduce the rate of granule disintegration, potentially impairing the rapid release of viable bacteria in gastrointestinal conditions. However, this same property might offer some protective effect against environmental stressors such as humidity and oxygen, suggesting a trade-off between mechanical stability and functional performance.

To address these limitations, further optimization is required. Strategies may include reducing binder concentration, incorporating disintegrants (e.g., cross-linked polymers), or modifying the granulation process parameters such as moisture content, mixing time, and drying conditions. Adjusting the ratio of maltodextrin and skim milk powder could also improve porosity and friability while maintaining probiotic viability.

Overall, while the current formulation ensures structural stability, its poor compliance with particle size standards and excessive hardness highlight the need for balancing mechanical properties with functional performance in probiotic granule development.

The resulting granule size did not pass through the standard sieve (0.2-1.4mm). The texture of the granules was dense and hard to break. Granules met the standards criteria for quantities of moulds and other microorganisms according to the Vietnamese Pharmacopoeia V (Pharmacopoeia, 1997).

Viable count assay of *L. acidophilus* cells in granules

The important thing of granules is the survival of bacteria. So, this study checked the survival of *L. acidophilus*. The study checked the growth for 1 month. The results show that the

bacteria still had a high survival rate 90 ± 4.7 to $95 \pm 2\%$. This means the granules can be used to develop products with *L. acidophilus*.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the present study that the probiotic *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356 can be incorporated with potential phycocyanin into the preparation of granules. It is necessary to continue monitoring the stability, moisture content, and disintegration of the tested granules for longer storage. For the future study, the viability of *L. acidophilus* in granules needs to be investigated when exposure to gut conditions.

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